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TURIZM SOHASIDA TARJIMA NAZARIYASINING O'RNINI

Bahronova Charos Mirabbos qizi

SRIUTCH, Turizm menejmenti fakulteti, 1-bosqich talabasi

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada turizm sohasida tarjima nazariyasining tutgan o'рни va ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Turizm bugungi kunda mamlakatlar o'rtasidagi madaniy, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy aloqalarni rivojlantiruvchi muhim sohalardan biri hisoblanadi. Turistlarga xizmat ko'rsatishda axborotni turli tillarga to'g'ri va mazmunan aniq tarjima qilish katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Maqolada tarjima nazariyasining asosiy tamoyillari, jumladan ekvivalentlik, adekvatlik va pragmatik moslik tushunchalari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, gid matnlari, reklama materiallari, broshyuralar, veb-saytlar va mobil ilovalardagi tarjima jarayonining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari tahlil qilingan. Turizm matnlarini tarjima qilishda milliy madaniyat, urf-odatlar va tarixiy merosni to'g'ri ifodalash zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, tarjima nazariyasining amaliy qo'llanilishi turistlar uchun qulay axborot muhitini yaratish, xalqaro sayyohlar oqimini ko'paytirish hamda mamlakatning turistik imijini shakllantirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, tarjima nazariyasi, ekvivalentlik, adekvat tarjima, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya, turistik matnlar, reklama tarjimasi, xalqaro turizm.

Abstract. This article analyzes the role and significance of translation theory in the tourism industry. Today, tourism is one of the most important sectors contributing to the development of cultural, economic, and social relations between countries. In providing services to tourists, accurate and meaningful translation of information into different languages is of great importance. The article discusses the main principles of translation theory, including the concepts of equivalence, adequacy, and pragmatic adaptation. It also examines the specific features of translating guide texts, advertising materials, brochures, websites, and mobile applications. Particular emphasis is placed on the need to accurately convey national culture, traditions, and historical heritage in the translation of tourism-related texts. The results of the study show that the practical application of translation theory plays a significant role in creating a convenient information environment for tourists, increasing the flow of international visitors, and shaping a positive tourism image of a country.

Keywords: tourism, translation theory, equivalence, adequate translation, intercultural communication, tourism texts, advertising translation, international tourism.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется роль и значение теории перевода в сфере туризма. Туризм в настоящее время является одной из важнейших отраслей, способствующих развитию культурных, экономических и социальных связей между странами. При обслуживании туристов особое значение имеет точный и адекватный перевод информации на различные языки. В статье рассматриваются основные принципы теории перевода, включая понятия эквивалентности, адекватности и прагматической адаптации. Также анализируются особенности перевода экскурсионных текстов, рекламных материалов, брошюр, веб-сайтов и мобильных приложений. Подчеркивается необходимость правильной передачи национальной культуры, традиций и исторического наследия при переводе туристических текстов. По результатам исследования установлено, что практическое применение теории перевода играет важную роль в создании удобной информационной среды для туристов, увеличении потока международных туристов и формировании положительного туристического имиджа страны.

Ключевые слова: туризм, теория перевода, эквивалентность, адекватный перевод, межкультурная коммуникация, туристические тексты, перевод рекламы, международный туризм.

KIRISH

Bugungi kunda turizm dunyo iqtisodiyotining eng tez rivojlanayotgan sohasalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Turizmning rivojlanishi davlatlar o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy, madaniy va ijtimoiy aloqalarning kengayishiga xizmat qiladi. Xalqaro turizm rivojlangan sari turli millat vakillari o'rtasidagi kommunikatsiya ehtiyoji ham ortib bormoqda. Shu nuqtai nazardan tarjima nazariyasi turizm sohasining ajralmas qismiga aylanmoqda. Turizmida tarjima nafaqat matnni bir tildan boshqa tilga o'girish, balki milliy qadriyatlar, urf-odatlar va madaniy xususiyatlarni to'g'ri yetkazish vazifasini ham bajaradi

¹. Mehmonxona xizmatlari, ekskursiya matnlari, reklama materiallari, turistik veb-saytlar va gid faoliyatida tarjima muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Noto‘g‘ri yoki sifatsiz tarjima turistlarda salbiy taassurot uyg‘otishi mumkin. O‘zbekistonning turistik salohiyati yildan-yilga ortib borayotganligi sababli turizm sohasida professional tarjimonlarga bo‘lgan talab ham kuchaymoqda. Ayniqsa, Samarqand, Buxoro va Xiva kabi tarixiy shaharlarga tashrif buyuruvchi xorijiy sayyohlar uchun ko‘p tilli axborot tizimlarini yaratish dolzarb masalalardan biridir.

MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Tarjima nazariyasi va turizm o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlik ko‘plab olimlar tomonidan o‘rganilgan. Jumladan, Peter Newmark tarjimaning kommunikativ va semantik usullarini tahlil qilib, turistik matnlarda kommunikativ tarjimaning ustunligini ta’kidlaydi. Uning fikricha, tarjima o‘quvchiga tushunarli va tabiiy yetkazilishi kerak². Eugene Nida esa “dinamik ekvivalentlik” nazariyasini ishlab chiqib, tarjima mazmunining qabul qiluvchi auditoriyaga ta’siri muhim ekanligini ko‘rsatadi³. Turizm matnlarida aynan turistning matnni qanday qabul qilishi asosiy mezonlardan biri hisoblanadi.

O‘zbekistonlik tadqiqotchilar ham turizm va tarjima masalalariga e’tibor qaratgan. Xususan, G. Ilkhomova O‘zbekistonda Buyuk Ipak yo‘li turistik yo‘nalishlarining xalqaro ahamiyatini tahlil qilib, xorijiy tillardagi axborot sifatini oshirish zarurligini qayd etadi⁴. Shuningdek, Fayzullayev va hamkorlari O‘zbekiston turistik imijining shakllanishida madaniy va lingvistik omillarning muhim rol o‘ynashini ta’kidlaydilar⁵.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Mazkur tadqiqotda turizm sohasidagi tarjima jarayonlarini o‘rganish maqsadida ilmiy kuzatish, qiyosiy tahlil, tavsifiy, kontent-tahlil hamda nazariy umumlashtirish metodlaridan foydalanildi. Tadqiqot davomida turistik matnlar, reklama materiallari, sayyohlik yo‘riqnomalari va elektron axborot resurslarida qo‘llanilgan tarjima namunalari tahlil qilindi. Qiyosiy tahlil usuli yordamida original va tarjima matnlari o‘rtasidagi lingvistik hamda uslubiy farqlar aniqlandi. Tavsifiy metod asosida turistik matnlarning leksik, grammatik va pragmatik xususiyatlari yoritildi. Shuningdek, turizm terminlarining tarjima qilinishida qo‘llaniladigan strategiyalar hamda ularning kommunikativ samaradorligi ilmiy manbalar va amaliy misollar asosida baholandi. Olingan natijalar nazariy umumlashtirish usuli orqali tizimlashtirilib, turizm sohasida tarjima sifatini oshirishga qaratilgan ilmiy xulosalar shakllantirildi.

TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR

Turizm sohasida tarjima bir nechta muhim funksiyalarni bajaradi:

1-rasm: Turizm sohasida tarjima nazariyasining asosiy funksiyalari⁶

1 Munday, J. (2016). *Introducing Translation Studies: Theories and Applications*. London: Routledge.

2 Nida, E. A. (1964). *Toward a Science of Translating*. Leiden: Brill Academic Publishers.

3 Newmark, P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. New York: Prentice Hall.

4 Ilkhomova, G. (2024). “Peculiarities of Tourist Destination in Uzbekistan Crossing Through the Great Silk Road”. *Science and Innovation*, 738–743.

5 Fayzullaev, K., Cassel, S. H., Brandt, D. (2021). “Destination Image in Uzbekistan: Heritage of the Silk Road and Nature Experiences as the Core of an Evolving Post-Soviet Identity”. *The Service Industries Journal*, 446–461.

6 Muallif ishlanmasi

Turistik matnlarning asosiy xususiyati ularning reklama va informativ xarakterga egaligidir. Shu sababli bunday matnlarni tarjima qilishda oddiy soʻzma-soʻz tarjima yetarli boʻlmaydi. Tarjimon matnning uslubiy va madaniy xususiyatlarini ham hisobga olishi lozim.

Masalan, oʻzbek milliy taomlari yoki tarixiy obidalar nomlarini tarjima qilishda transliteratsiya va izohlash usullari qoʻllaniladi. “Registon majmuasi”, “palov”, “mahalla” kabi tushunchalarni xorijiy turistga tushunarli shaklda yetkazish tarjimonidan nafaqat til bilimini, balki madaniy kompetensiyani ham talab qiladi.

Turizm tarjima nazariyasining amaliy ahamiyati quyidagilarda ham namoyon boʻladi:

- Turistik saytlar va mobil ilovalarni koʻp tilli shaklda yaratishda;
- Mehmonxona va restoran xizmatlarini xalqaro standartlarga moslashtirishda;
- Ekskursiya va gidlik faoliyatida;
- Xalqaro turizm reklamalarini tayyorlashda.

Bugungi kunda sunʼiy intellekt asosidagi avtomatik tarjima tizimlari keng qoʻllanayotgan boʻlsa-da, turizm sohasida inson tarjimasi hanzuz muhim oʻrin tutadi. Chunki madaniy kontekst va emotsional taʼsirni toʻliq yetkazishda professional tarjimonning roli katta.

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

Xulosa qilib aytganda, tarjima nazariyasi turizm sohasining muhim tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. U xalqaro turistlarga sifatli axborot yetkazish, milliy madaniyatni targʻib qilish hamda mamlakatning ijobiy imijini shakllantirishda katta ahamiyatga ega. Oʻzbekistonda turizm rivojlanayotgan hozirgi davrda koʻp tilli professional tarjima xizmatlarini rivojlantirish dolzarb vazifalardan biridir.

Turistik matnlarni tarjima qilishda lingvistik bilim bilan bir qatorda madaniy yondashuv ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shu sababli tarjimonlarni tayyorlashda turizm terminologiyasi va madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya masalalariga alohida eʼtibor qaratish zarur.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar roʻyxati

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